

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF THE RANGE OF ANTIALLERGIC DRUGS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR 2021-2025

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Relevance: currently, the prevalence of allergic diseases is constantly increasing. Allergic diseases and their complications lead to a decrease in the quality of life and an increase in the need for anti-allergic drugs. In this regard, there is a need to study the pharmaceutical market of antiallergic drugs, which will allow us to determine how modern the range of this group of drugs is in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Purpose of the study: the purpose of our work was to analyze anti-allergic drugs in the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan for 2021-2025.

Materials and methods: the materials of this study were the State Registers of drugs and medical equipment registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2025 (No. 25-29), which were subjected to content analysis.

Results: in Uzbekistan in 2021, 210 trade names of anti-allergic drugs were registered, among which 30.95% of domestic, 51.90% of imported production and 17.14% of production of CIS countries. In 2022, 206 trade names of anti-allergic drugs were registered, among which 29.12% of domestic, 53.88% of imported production and 16.99% of production of CIS countries. In 2023, 201 trade names of anti-allergic drugs were registered, including 31.80% of domestic, 52.30% of imported production and 15.90% of production of CIS countries. In 2024, 213 trade names of anti-allergic drugs were registered, including 33.90% of domestic, 48.80% of imported production and 17.20% of production of CIS countries. According to the results of the analysis, it was found that the range of antiallergic drugs as a whole has increased. In 2024, 219 trade names of anti-allergic drugs were registered, including 35.19% of domestic, 51.10% of imported production and 13.71% of production of CIS countries. According to the results of the analysis, it was found that the range of antiallergic drugs as a whole has increased:

Years	The general range of anti-allergic drugs	Anti-allergic drugs of manufacturers of		
		Uzbekistan	CIS countries	Foreign countries
2021	210	65	36	109
2022	206	60	35	111
2023	201	62	36	103
2024	213	72	35	96
2025	219	77	30	112

A comparative analysis of the range of anti-allergic drugs by producing countries was also carried out. The data obtained indicate that anti-allergic drugs are presented in a wide range. Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the largest number of antiallergic drugs falls on the share of Uzbekistan (41.91%), then India (20.66%), Turkey (8.10%), Russia (6.40%) and Ukraine (5.65%).

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Conclusions: during the research period, there was a tendency to increase the number and share of trade names of anti-allergic drugs of foreign and domestic production. The increase in the number of anti-allergic drugs of domestic production in the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan is of great social and economic importance.